

OKSIDLANISH-QAYTARILISH REAKSIYALARINI MATEMATIK USULDA TENGLASHTIRISH

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KIRISH

Oksidlanish-qaytarilish reaksiyalari elektronlarning atomlardan atomlarga butunlay yoki qisman olish yoki berishi bilan bog'liq kimyoviy reaksiyalardir. Elektronlar chiqarilishi oksidlanish, elektronlar biriktirib olishi qaytarilish deyiladi.

Oksidlanish-qaytarilish reaksiyalarini quyidagi usullar yordamida tenglashtirishimiz mumkin;

- ❖ Elektrobilans usuli
- ❖ Ion-balans usuli
- ❖ Kislород usuli
- ❖ Matematik usul

Biz hozir oksidlanish-qaytarilish reaksiyalarini matematik usulda tenglashtirishni o'rganamiz. Oksidlanish-qaytarilish reaksiyalarini xarakterlovchi tenglamalar tuzishdagi qoidalar quyidagicha; "Reaksiyada ishtirok etayotgan har qaysi elementlarning atomlar soni oksidlanish-qaytarilish reaksiyasi tenglamasining chap va o'ng tomonlarida teng bo'lishi, bundan tashqari tenglamaning chap va o'ng tomondagi zaryadlarning algebraik yig'indisi teng bo'lishi shart". Yuqoridagi qoidadan foydalanib NaNO_2 ni kislotali sharoitda KMnO_4 ishtirokida oksidlanish-qaytarilish reaksiyasini matematik usulda tenglashtiramiz.

NaNO_2 va KMnO_4 lar oldidagi koeffitsiyentini mos ravishda x va y bilan belgilaymiz, H_2SO_4 ni oldiga koeffitsiyent qo'ymay turamiz chunki, S atomi tenglamaning chap tomonida bitta modda tarkibida, o'ng tomonda esa ikkita modda tarkibida bor bo'lganligi uchun o'ng tomondagi S atomi bor birikmalar oldiga koeffitsiyent qo'ymasdan turib, H_2SO_4 ni oldiga koeffitsiyent qo'yolmaymiz.

Endi tenglamani chap va o'ng tomonidagi Na atomini tenglashtiramiz. Tenglamani chap tomonida x ta Na atomi bor, o'ng tomonda esa 1 ta Na atomi bor, tenglashtirish uchun NaNO_3 ni oldiga x koeffitsiyentini qo'yamiz.

Endi esa ushbu reaksiyadagi K atomini tenglashtiramiz. K atomi chap tomonda y ta, o'ng tomonda esa ikkita K atomi bor, biz tenglashtirishimiz uchun K_2SO_4 ni oldidan $y/2$ koeffitsiyentini joylashtiramiz.

Endi chap va o'ng tomondagi Mn atomlarini tenglashtiramiz. Chap tomonda Mn atomi y ta

bor, o'ngda esa bitta bor, bunday holatda tenglashtirishimiz uchun $MnSO_4$ tuzining oldiga y koeffitsiyentini yozamiz.

Tenglashtirishimizni davom etamiz, chap va o'ng tomondagi S (oltingugurt) atomlarini tenglashtiramiz. O'ng tomondagi S atomlari soni $y+y/2$ va tenglashtirishimiz uchun chap tomondagi H_2SO_4 ni oldiga $y+y/2$ koeffitsiyentini qo'yamiz.

Endi tenglamamizdan H atomini tenglashtiramiz. Chap tomondagi H atomlari $y+y/2$ taga teng, tenglashtirishimiz uchun H_2O molekulasining oldiga $y+y/2$ koeffitsiyentini yozamiz.

Endi esa faqatgina N atomi qoldi. N atomi chap tomonda ham o'ng tomonda ham tengligi sabali tenglashtirishimiz shart emas.

Tenglamadagi barcha moddaning oldiga koeffitsiyentlarini qoyib oldik. Endi esa yuqoridagi qoidaga ko'ra O atomlarini tenglashtiramiz. Tenglamaning chap tomonida $2x+4y+(y+y/2)$ ta atom bor, o'ng tomonda esa $3x+4y+4(y/2)+(y+y/2)$ ta O atomi bor. Tenglamaning chap va o'ng tomondagi O atomlarini sonini quyidagi ifoda tenglashtiramiz.

$$2x+4y+(y+y/2) = 3x+4y+4(y/2)+(y+y/2)$$

$$2x+4y+2 \cdot 3y = 3x+2y+4y+3y/2$$

Endi tenglamdagi x va y larni mos ravishda qo'shib olamiz.

$$2x+10y=3x+6y+3y/2$$

$$10y-6y-3y/2=3x-2x$$

$$4y-3y/2=x$$

$$5y/2=x$$

$$2x=5y$$

Endi tenglamani tanlash yo'li bilan davom ettiramiz

Endi $x=5$ $y=2$ qiymatlarni moddalar oldiga qo'yamiz. $NaNO_2$ ning oldida x bor, demak bu qiymat $[x=5]$ ga teng, bu qiymatni $NaNO_2$ ning oldiga qo'yamiz.

$KMnO_4$ ni oldidiga y koeffitsiyent qo'yilgan demak, $KMnO_4$ ni oldiga $[y=2]$ koeffitsiyent qo'yamiz.

H_2SO_4 ni oldida $y+y/2$ koeffitsiyent qo'yilgan, bunga y ning qiymatini qo'ysak bu qiymat $[2+2/2=3]$ ga teng bo'ladi demak, H_2SO_4 ni oldiga 3 koeffitsiyentini qo'yamiz.

$NaNO_3$ ni oldida x koeffitsiyenti qo'yilgan demak, bu yerga $[x=5]$ koeffitsiyentini qo'yamiz.

$MnSO_4$ ni oldida y koeffitsiyenti bor demak, bu moddaning oldiga $[y=2]$ koeffitsiyentini qo'yamiz.

K_2SO_4 ni oldida $y/2$ koeffitsiyent bor demak, $[2/2=1]$ koeffitsiyentini ushbu tuzning oldiga qo'yamiz.

H₂O molekulasining oldida $y+y/2$ koeffitsiyenti bor demak, $[2+2/2=3]$ koeffitsiyentini suvning oldiga qo'yamiz.

Endi chap va o'ng tomondagi atomlar sonini tengligini tekshirib ko'ramiz. Na atomlari chap tomonda ham o'ng tomonda ham 5 ta ekan demak Na atomlari teng. N atomlari ham chap tomonda ham o'ng tomonda 5 ta va ular teng. K atomlari chap tomonda 2 ta va o'ng tomonda ham 2 ta demak, ular teng. Mn atomlari ham xuddi shunday 2ta chap tomonda ham o'ng tomonda ham, ular ham teng. Endi H atomlarini tekshiramiz, ushbu atom chap tomonda $[3*2=6]$ 6ta va o'ng tomonda $[3*2=6]$ 6 ta, albatta, bu atomlar ham teng. S atomlari o'ng tomonda $[2+1=3]$ 3 ta ekan, o'ng tomonda ham 3 ta shu atom bor demak, ular ham teng. Va oxirida O atomlarini tengligini tekshiramiz. Chap tomonda O atomlari $[2*5+2*4+3*4=30]$ 30 ta ekan, o'ngda esa $[5*3+2*8+1*4+3*1=30]$ 30 ta demak, kislorod atomlari ham teng ekan. Reaksiyaning o'ng va chapdagi barcha atomlar tenglashdi demak, reaksiyamiz tenglashdi.

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